

BONDED REPAIR OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

Aris Khechen¹, Marie-Laure Dano¹, Augustin Gakwaya¹ and Chun Li²

¹Department of Mechanical Engineering, Laval University
1065 Avenue de la médecine, Québec, QC G1V 0A6, Canada
Email: aris.khechen.1@ulaval.ca, web page: <http://mcs-ulaval.ca/>

²Structures, Materials and Manufacturing Lab, Aerospace, National Research Council Canada
1200 Montreal Road, Building M-3, Ottawa, ON K1A 0R6, Canada
Email: Chun.Li@nrc-cnrc.gc.ca

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on testing and modeling of bonded scarf-stepped composite joint performance under uniaxial tensile loading as part of the effort to develop testing protocols and analytical tools for the design of scarf bonded repair for primary aerospace composite structures. In this study, the effects of environmental condition (room temperature dry (RTD) and elevated temperature dry (ETD) and scarf angle (at 3° and 7.5°) on the performance of the bonded repairs were investigated. The tensile test results revealed that scarf angle has a significant impact on the failure mode of the repaired composite part. While substrate failure occurred for the 3° scarf angle repair, cohesive shear failure was observed for the 7.5° scarf angle repair. This change in failure mode is consistent for both repaired exposed to RTD and ETD. As compared to that of the pristine laminate, a 2% and 4% drop in stiffness was found for the 3° and 7.5° scarf angle repairs, respectively. An 85% and 40% strength restitution was found for the 3° and 7.5° scarf angle repairs, respectively, indicating the importance of scarf angle on the structural integrity of scarf-stepped bonded repair. The tensile test results at ETD suggest there is only a slight decrease in stiffness and strength for both repairs at ETD in comparison to RTD. 2D through-thickness finite-element analyses were also conducted using both ABAQUS Standard and Explicit. An elastic analysis was first performed to predict the distribution of normalized shear and peel stresses in the middle of the adhesive along the bondline for different joint geometries. Next, an elastic-plastic analysis was conducted using the already implemented plasticity and shear damage models in ABAQUS. These plasticity and damage models were used for the adhesive film only. The composite material was supposed to behave linear-elastically up to failure. The maximum strain criterion was used to predict the first ply failure in the composite. The predictions obtained with the model correlated very well with the experimental results.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials have been increasingly used for primary aircraft components because of their superior structural performances such as high specific strength and stiffness, long fatigue life, and being lightweight. Although composite structures offer many advantages over traditional metallic structures, they are more sensitive to other types of damage such as impact. Impact can cause delamination, matrix cracks, fiber failure and material crushing which can induce severe reductions in strength and stiffness and may lead to structural failure. Therefore, it is crucial to have effective repair methods to restore the stiffness and strength of damaged composite structures.

Adhesively bonded scarf repairs are widely used to repair monolithic and sandwich aircraft structures [1]. Parameters such as the scarf angle of the bonded repairs, the adhesive thickness, the adherends material type and the stacking sequence of the repair patch have been shown both experimentally and numerically to have a great influence on mechanical properties of the repaired structure [2, 3]. Three numerical approaches have been used to describe the constitutive behaviour of the bondline and to predict failure of bonded scarf repairs, namely, the Virtual Crack Closure Technique (VCCT) [4], the Cohesive Zone Model (CZM) [5], and the elastic-plastic model with shear

failure criterion [3, 6]. The first two approaches have the advantage of being able to run on ABAQUS/Standard, which reduces the calculation cost and analysis time. However, they require determining the elastic and plastic properties in shear of the adhesive film from lap shear tests, as well as the critical strain energy release rates from DCB, ENF and MMB testing. Also, they require that the crack path is known. The elastic-plastic model with shear failure criterion approach presents the advantages of only requiring determining the elastic-plastic properties in shear of the adhesive film. The crack path and therefore the failure mode of the adhesive (i.e.: cohesive, adhesive or mixed mode failure) can be predicted. However, this kind of analysis, which includes a damage evolution law, can only be run in ABAQUS/Explicit, which can lead to high calculation cost and analysis time.

The general objective of the paper is to develop analytical tools and protocols for the design of scarf bonded repairs for primary aerospace composite structures. Scarf bonded repair is performed on monolithic composite panels made of woven carbon fabric/epoxy quasi-isotropic laminates. The laminates are made of new out-of-autoclave (OOA) prepreg. The specific objectives of this study are: (i) to develop a 2D elastic finite-element model to predict accurately the stress distribution and rupture in the adherends and the adhesive, (ii) to investigate the effects of geometrical and material parameters (scarf type and angle, material) on the strength of the repair, and (iii) to investigate the effects of temperature on the strength of the repair.

First, the paper presents a 2D linear elastic numerical analysis conducted to investigate the peel and shear stress distributions along the bondline for three types of joint configurations. Then, a 2D non-linear elastic-plastic analysis is conducted to predict the failure mode and strength of 3° and 7.5° scarf-step bonded repairs. Finally, 3° and 7.5° scarf angle bonded repairs are tested in tension at room and elevated temperatures. Results are then compared with the model predictions.

2 LINEAR ELASTIC NUMERICAL MODEL

In this section, both pristine and repaired quasi-isotropic specimens loaded under uniaxial tension have been modeled using ABAQUS/Standard. The analysis is divided into two parts. The first part is a through-the-thickness 2D model of a pristine quasi-isotropic laminate with a $[+45^\circ/0^\circ/-45^\circ/90^\circ]_{2s}$ stacking sequence. The objective of this first analysis is to validate the prediction of the effective elastic modulus of the laminate when modeled in the (x,z) plan. Once the appropriate composite material properties and modeling approach have been identified, the repaired specimens were then modeled. The second part is a through-the-thickness 2D model of three different repaired specimens geometric configurations, namely scarf-scarf (C1), scarf-step (C2), and step-step (C3). This analysis provides the peel and shear stress distributions along the bondline in the middle of the adhesive for a 3° scarf angle repair of a quasi-isotropic laminate. In order to be compared with one-another, these stresses have been normalized by the applied stress. These stress distributions highlight where failure is most likely to occur for each geometric configuration, as well as which configuration is the most efficient in terms of generating the minimum stress magnitude along the bondline.

2.1 FINITE ELEMENT MODELING OF THE PRISTINE QUASI-ISOTROPIC LAMINATE

A thin slice of a quasi-isotropic laminate was modeled through-the-thickness in the (x,z) plane. This slice is 170 mm long and 3.04 mm thick. Each one of the 16 plies of the quasi-isotropic stacking sequence has been modeled, in order to account for the stiffness variation through the thickness. The composite material is a plain weave (PW) carbon fiber-reinforced plastic (CFRP). Each ply has a 0.19 mm thickness. The elastic material properties used in the analysis are given in Table 1.

Property	Units	PW Material
$E_1 = E_2$	[GPa]	64.6
E_3	[GPa]	14.0
$G_{12} = G_{23} = G_{13}$	[GPa]	4.93
$\nu_{12} = \nu_{23} = \nu_{13}$	-	0.047

Table 1: Elastic properties of a PW CFRP at RTD

The values for E_1 , E_2 , G_{12} and ν_{12} were determined experimentally. Moduli E_1 and E_2 were found to be slightly different. In order to avoid the appearance of coupling terms in the computed stiffness matrices, the moduli were assumed to be identical and equal to:

$$E_1 = E_2 = \frac{E_1 + E_2}{2} \quad (1)$$

The elastic properties of Table 1 were used to compute the 3D stiffness matrix of the plane weave ply. Since the same elastic properties were assumed in the 1- and 2- directions, the stiffness matrix is the same for the 0° and 90° plies, as well as for the $+45^\circ$ and -45° plies. First, the compliance matrix $[S(0^\circ)]$ was calculated from the engineering constants given in Table 1 using [7]:

$$[S] = \begin{bmatrix} 1/E_1 & -\nu_{21}/E_2 & -\nu_{31}/E_3 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\nu_{12}/E_1 & 1/E_2 & -\nu_{32}/E_3 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\nu_{13}/E_1 & -\nu_{23}/E_2 & 1/E_3 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{23} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{13} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{12} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Then, the compliance matrix $[\bar{S}(45^\circ)]$ was calculated using:

$$[\bar{S}(45^\circ)] = [T'(45^\circ)][S][T(45^\circ)] \quad (3)$$

where $[T(45^\circ)]$ is the coordinate transformation matrix and is given by:

$$[T(45^\circ)] = \begin{bmatrix} \cos^2(45) & \sin^2(45) & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2\cos(45)\sin(45) \\ \sin^2(45) & \cos^2(45) & 0 & 0 & 0 & -2\cos(45)\sin(45) \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \cos(45) & -\sin(45) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \sin(45) & \cos(45) & 0 \\ -\cos(45)\sin(45) & \cos(45)\sin(45) & 0 & 0 & 0 & \cos^2(45) - \sin^2(45) \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Finally, the calculated compliance matrices were then inverted to calculate the stiffness matrices $[C(0^\circ)]$ and $[\bar{C}(45^\circ)]$ using:

$$[C(\theta)] = [S^{-1}(\theta)] \quad (5)$$

The lines and columns of the calculated stiffness matrices were then swapped a first time to meet ABAQUS convention, and then a second time, since the thickness was modeled along the y-axis instead of the z-axis, as explained in Figure 1.

Standard convention	ABAQUS convention	Thickness along y-axis
$\begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{21} & C_{22} & C_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{31} & C_{32} & C_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{55} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{66} \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{21} & C_{22} & C_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{31} & C_{32} & C_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{66} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{55} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{44} \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{13} & C_{12} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{31} & C_{33} & C_{32} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{21} & C_{23} & C_{22} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{55} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{66} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{44} \end{bmatrix}$

Figure 1: Stiffness matrices swapping procedure according to the modeling convention

The left end of the laminate was fully constrained and a pressure was applied along the x-axis on the other end to simulate a tensile test. The laminate section was modeled using different solid elements (plane stress, plane strain and generalized plane strain) as summarized in Table 2. The objective was to determine which element was the most suitable to predict the elastic behaviour of the laminate. Results provided by the Composite Laminate Theory (CLT) were used for comparison.

Approach	2D Planar (Deformable Shell)		CLT
Section	Solid (Homogeneous)		Solid Laminate
Elements	Plane Stress (CPS4)	Plane Strain (CPE4)	Generalized Plane Strain (CPEG4)
Results	E = 40.9 GPa	E = 51.8 GPa	E = 46.8 GPa

Table 2: Effective elastic modulus prediction for a quasi-isotropic laminate using multiple modeling approaches

CLT predicted an effective elastic modulus of 46.8 GPa. As can be observed in Table 2, the effective elastic modulus predicted by generalized plane strain elements is the closest to the one predicted by CLT. The effective elastic modulus obtained with plane strain elements is overestimated by 10%. It can be corrected using the correcting factor, C_f , defined by:

$$C_f = \frac{46.8}{51.8} = 0.9 \quad (6)$$

On the other hand, plane stress elements underestimated the effective elastic modulus by 14.5%.

2.2 FINITE ELEMENT MODELING OF THE REPAIRED LAMINATE

Once the numerical model for the laminate was validated, the elastic analysis of the repaired laminate was conducted using generalized plane strain elements. Three geometric repair configurations were modeled. The first geometric configuration, shown in Figure 2, is a scarf-scarf (C1) repair, where both parent and patch bonding surface areas are smooth. The second geometric configuration, shown in Figure 3, is a scarf-step (C2) repair, where the parent bonding surface area is smooth and the patch bonding surface area is stepped. The third geometric configuration, shown in Figure 4, is a step-step (C3) repair, where both parent and patch bonding surface areas are stepped. For the three configurations, the scarf angle was constant and equal to 3° , the adhesive thickness was constant and equal to 0.25 mm and the stacking sequence was $[+45^\circ/0^\circ/-45^\circ/90^\circ]_{2s}$.

Figure 2: Geometry of a 16-ply 3° scarf angle quasi-isotropic scarf-scarf (C1) repair

Figure 3: Geometry of a 16-ply 3° scarf angle quasi-isotropic scarf-step (C2) repair

Figure 4: Geometry of a 16-ply 3° scarf angle quasi-isotropic step-step (C3) repair

The adhesive film was modeled between the parent and the patch and was considered as an isotropic elastic material with elastic properties given in the following:

Property	Units	Adhesive Film
E	[GPa]	3.25
ν	[-]	0.3

Table 3: Elastic properties of the adhesive film (0.25mm) at RTD

After the analysis was run for each configuration using ABAQUS/Standard, the stiffness of the repaired laminate was calculated. The results are shown in Table 4. The elastic stiffness of the pristine laminate is added for comparison.

Configuration	Pristine laminate	Scarf – Scarf (C1)	Scarf – Step (C2)	Step – Step (C3)
Elastic stiffness [GPa]	46.8	44.7	43.6	42.3

Table 4: Stiffness prediction of repaired quasi-isotropic laminates using different bonded joint configurations

As can be noticed in Table 4, the repair generates a loss of 7% in the global stiffness compared to the pristine quasi-isotropic structure. Since the adhesive has a lower elastic modulus than the composite material, the repaired laminate is expected to be less stiff than the pristine one. Also, it appears that the joint geometry affects the global stiffness of the whole repaired laminate. Scarf-scarf (C1) configuration restitutes the stiffness better than the scarf-step (C2) configuration, which is also stiffer than the step-step (C3) configuration.

In order to have a better understanding of the mechanical behaviour of the repair joint, it is relevant to observe the distribution of the peel and shear stresses along the bondline. The stresses were determined in the middle of the adhesive and for the three configurations. Stresses were normalized by the far-field stress to make comparison easier.

Figure 5 compares the normalized peel and shear stresses distributions along the normalized bondline for the scarf-scarf configuration (C1). Both peel and shear stresses distributions are perfectly symmetric. Shear stresses are significantly higher than peel stresses along the bondline. Also, high peak stresses are observed near both ends of the bondline. These stresses are found to be seven times higher in shear than in peel. Failure is most likely to occur at these specific regions.

Figure 5: Normalized peel and shear stresses vs. normalized bondline distance for a 3° scarf angle quasi-isotropic scarf-scarf (C1) repair

Figure 6 compares the normalized peel and shear stresses distributions along the normalized bondline for the scarf-step configuration (C2). Stresses distributions are asymmetric with higher stress concentrations near the top end of the bondline. Shear stresses are higher than peel stresses all along the bondline. Also, high peak stresses are present near the top end of the bondline. These stresses are found to be 2.5 times higher in shear than in peel. As opposed to shear stresses, no peel peak stresses are found at the bottom end of the bondline. Shear stresses are found to be 1.15 times higher at the top end of than at the bottom end of the bondline. Therefore, failure is most likely to occur at the top end region of the bondline.

Figure 6: Normalized peel and shear stresses vs. normalized bondline distance for a 3° scarf angle quasi-isotropic scarf-step (C2) repair

Figure 7 compares the normalized peel and shear stresses distributions along the normalized bondline for the step-step configuration (C3). Both peel and shear stresses distributions are perfectly symmetric. Shear stresses are found to be higher than peel stresses along the whole bondline. High peak stresses are present near both ends of the bondline. These stresses are twice as low as the peel stresses. Failure is most likely to occur at these specific regions.

Figure 7: Normalized peel and shear stresses vs. normalized bondline distance for a 3° scarf angle quasi-isotropic step-step (C3) repair

Figure 8 compares the normalized shear stresses distributions along the normalized bondline for the different repair configurations C1, C2 and C3. Configuration C1 shows the lowest shear stress distribution when compared to configurations C2 and C3. Configuration C3 exhibits the most frequent stress peaks. The highest stress peaks are observed for configuration C2 but they are almost equal to the ones observed for configuration C3.

Figure 8: Normalized shear stresses vs. normalized bondline distance for 3° scarf angle quasi-isotropic scarf-scarf (C1), scarf-step (C2) and step-step (C3) repairs

Figure 9 compares the normalized peel stresses distributions along the normalized bondline for the different repair configurations C1, C2 and C3. Configuration C1 shows the lowest shear stress distribution when compared to C2 and C3. Configuration C3 exhibits the most frequent stress peaks. Configurations C2 and C3 have shown to have the same stress peak at the top end of the bondline. Those same stress peaks can be found at the bottom end of the bondline but only for configuration C3. This indicates that the top ply of the patch and the bottom ply of the parent induce stress concentrations in peel when a step-step joint is used.

Figure 9: Normalized peel stresses vs. normalized bondline distance of 3° scarf angle quasi-isotropic scarf-scarf (C1), scarf-step (C2) and step-step (C3) repairs

3 NON-LINEAR ELASTIC-PLASTIC NUMERICAL MODEL

Once the linear elastic analysis was completed, a non-linear analysis of a repaired laminate under tensile loading was conducted using ABAQUS/Explicit. This analysis takes into account the elastic-plastic behaviour of the adhesive film as well as its failure mode. The repair configurations and the laminate stacking sequence were the same as in the elastic model. Two scarf angles were selected (3° and 7.5°) to study the influence of scarf angle on failure strength and mode. The pressure load was replaced by an applied displacement in the x-direction. Since generalized plane strain elements (CPEG4) are not available in the ABAQUS/Explicit element library, they were changed to plane strain elements (CPE4). This leads to an over-estimation of the calculated stiffness which was corrected using the correcting factor, C_f , calculated in Equation (6).

The elastic-plastic behaviour of the adhesive was implemented from experimental data [8] obtained from ASTM D5656 Thick Adherend Shear Test (TAST), which was idealized in order to reduce the number of values in the data array to be implemented in ABAQUS.

Among the different plasticity models available in ABAQUS, the von Mises-like yield criterion was selected to model the adhesive film [5, 6]. ABAQUS requires both elastic and plastic properties as input data when using the von Mises yield criterion. The equivalent von Mises stress, Equation (7), is compared with the yield stress to determine if the onset of plastic yielding has occurred [10].

$$\sigma^e = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}[(\sigma_x - \sigma_y)^2 + (\sigma_y - \sigma_z)^2 + (\sigma_z - \sigma_x)^2 + 6(\sigma_{xy}^2 + \sigma_{yz}^2 + \sigma_{xz}^2)]} \quad (7)$$

Since the adhesive is assumed to be loaded primarily in shear, the effective shear stress, τ^p , was derived from the equivalent von Mises stress as in:

$$\tau^p = \frac{\sigma^e}{\sqrt{3}} \quad (8)$$

The shear strain, γ , was converted into the absolute plastic strain, γ^p , using:

$$\gamma^p = \gamma - \frac{\tau}{G} \quad (9)$$

where G is the adhesive shear modulus.

The equivalent von Mises strain is then used to compute the corresponding equivalent strain at the onset of plastic yielding and beyond. It is given by:

$$\varepsilon^e = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} [(\varepsilon_x - \varepsilon_y)^2 + (\varepsilon_y - \varepsilon_z)^2 + (\varepsilon_z - \varepsilon_x)^2 + \frac{1}{2}(\varepsilon_{xy}^2 + \varepsilon_{yz}^2 + \varepsilon_{xz}^2)]} \quad (10)$$

The effective shear strain is derived from the equivalent von Mises strain as in:

$$\gamma^p = \sqrt{3}\varepsilon^e \quad (11)$$

Table 5 shows the hardening data that were entered in ABAQUS to model the plasticity of the adhesive film.

Yield Stress, σ^e [MPa]	Plastic Strain, ε^e [-]
25	0.00
65	0.01
75	0.04
80	0.15

Table 5: Adhesive film (0.25 mm, RTD) plasticity data implemented in ABAQUS/Explicit

In addition to the plasticity model, a shear failure criterion was used to predict failure of the adhesive. The value of this criterion is calculated from the plastic strains using:

$$\omega = \frac{\bar{\varepsilon}_0^{pl} + \sum \Delta \bar{\varepsilon}^{pl}}{\bar{\varepsilon}_f^{pl}} \quad (12)$$

Once this criterion is met (i.e.: $\omega = 1$) within an element, it is removed.

Table 6 shows the predicted failure stress for each joint configuration at 3° and 7.5° scarf angles at RTD. The stiffness was corrected using the previously determined correction factor C_f . The data presented for the pristine quasi-isotropic laminates were experimentally determined. Two types of failure stress were computed according to the failure mode. Since only the adhesive has a damage criterion implemented, the analysis was run until adhesive failure occurred. The corresponding applied stress is called adhesive failure stress and is noted as σ_{fail_adh} . Then, axial strain was computed in the 0° plies, where failure was assumed to occur first. Once the axial strain was found greater than 1.3% [11] (corrected using C_f to be consistent with the plane strain analysis) in a 0° ply, failure of the composite was assumed to occur. The corresponding applied stress is called composite failure stress and is noted σ_{fail_comp} . If $\sigma_{fail_comp} < 0.95 \sigma_{fail_adh}$ failure was assumed to occur in the composite and $\sigma_{fail} = \sigma_{fail_comp}$. If $\sigma_{fail_comp} > 0.95 \sigma_{fail_adh}$ failure was assumed to occur in the composite and the adhesive and $\sigma_{fail_comp} < \sigma_{fail} < \sigma_{fail_adh}$. If $\sigma_{fail_comp} > \sigma_{fail_adh}$ failure was assumed to occur in the adhesive and $\sigma_{fail} = \sigma_{fail_adh}$. The 0.95 factor was arbitrarily determined in order to facilitate the interpretation of the results. Figure 10 summarizes the post-processing analysis procedure.

Configuration	Pristine Laminate [11]	Scarf – Scarf (C1)		Scarf – Step (C2)		Step – Step (C3)	
		$\alpha = 3^\circ$	$\alpha = 7.5^\circ$	$\alpha = 3^\circ$	$\alpha = 7.5^\circ$	$\alpha = 3^\circ$	$\alpha = 7.5^\circ$
Angle	-	$\alpha = 3^\circ$	$\alpha = 7.5^\circ$	$\alpha = 3^\circ$	$\alpha = 7.5^\circ$	$\alpha = 3^\circ$	$\alpha = 7.5^\circ$
Stiffness [GPa]	45.5	44.2	44.4	43.1	43.3	41.9	42.3
σ_{fail_adh} [MPa]	-	849	338	611	309	552	283
σ_{fail_comp} [MPa]	-	555	> 338	493	> 309	439	> 283
σ_{fail} [MPa]	653	555	338	493	309	439	283
Failure mode	Comp.	Comp.	Adh.	Comp.	Adh.	Comp.	Adh.

Table 6: Summary of explicit elastic-plastic analysis results for 3° and 7.5° scarf angle quasi-isotropic repairs with different geometric configurations C1, C2 and C3 at RTD

Figure 10: Diagram of the post-processing analysis used for determining the correct failure mode and failure stress of a quasi-isotropic repaired laminate

4 EXPERIMENTAL MANUFACTURING AND TESTING PROCEDURES

4.1 MANUFACTURING PROCEDURE

Scarf-stepped joints were made from CYCOM 5320 PW epoxy resin with a plain weave fiber architecture (T650-35 3K PW, 196 g/m² areal weight, 36 % resin content) adherends from Cytec Engineering Materials and Cytec FM 300-2M (293 g/m² areal weight) adhesive film. A quasi-isotropic stacking sequence [+45°/0°/-45°/90°]_{2s} was used for both the parent and the patch. First, 150 mm-long by 150 mm-wide plies were cut from a 0.19 mm-thick prepreg. Then, in order to obtain the desired 3° and 7.5° scarf angles, 16 plies were carefully hand-laid to build the quasi-isotropic parent laminate, each one spaced of a $L_{overlap}$ distance, calculated using Equation (13):

$$L_{overlap} = \frac{t_{ply}}{\tan(\alpha)} \quad (13)$$

with $L_{overlap}$ being the distance between each overlying ply of the layup, t_{ply} is the ply thickness, and α is the scarf angle.

The parent laminate was then cured in an oven at 177 °C under vacuum after a 6-hour debulk period.

After curing, the step shaped parent laminate was sanded using a pneumatic disk sander with P180-grit sandpaper. Once the bonding surface was sanded until evenly smoothed (i.e.: scarf shaped) and completely free of resin, it was thoroughly cleaned with acetone and then dried using cotton cheesecloth.

The patch was then assembled using the same procedure as the parent. The 0.25 mm-thick adhesive film was placed between the sanded parent and the step shaped patch. The whole assembly was then cured following the same cure cycle as the one used for the parent laminate. Figure 11 shows a representation of the repair. The panel was finally cut into 250 mm-long and 25 mm-wide specimens using waterjet.

Figure 11: Representation of the bonded repair

4.2 TESTING PROCEDURE

Specimens were tested in tension using a 100 kN MTS machine at a crosshead speed of 4 mm/min at RTD and ETD conditions. No tabs were used since the laminate is quasi-isotropic. Emery cloth was used as stipulated by the ASTM D3039/3039M standard. Load was measured directly from the traction machine. Axial strain was recorded using a video-extensometer. Local strain was measured by a 3D optical measurement system (ARAMIS GOM) but only at RTD since the glass in the environmental chamber door does not allow getting accurate data with this measuring method. Therefore, only the video-extensometer was used to acquire strains at ETD.

For the ETD tests, specimens were placed in an environmental chamber at a temperature of 82°C. The specimen temperature was recorded using a thermocouple. Once the desired temperature was reached, 5 minutes were elapsed before starting the test.

5 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND COMPARISON

5.1 TEST RESULTS OF A 3° SCARF ANGLE FOR QUASI-ISOTROPIC SCARF-STEP (C2) REPAIR AT RTD AND ETD

Three specimens per condition were tested at RTD and at ETD. Each specimen failed in the composite material at an average failure stress of 558 MPa at RTD and 545 MPa at ETD. This corresponds to a 2.3% reduction in strength. The stiffness was found to be equal to 44.4 GPa on average at RTD and equal to 42.2 GPa on average at ETD. This corresponds to a 5% reduction in stiffness. At RTD, specimens 1 and 3 failed at the junction between the patch and the parent, at the top part of the repair. Specimen 2 failed away from the bondline, in the patch, as shown in Figure 12. At ETD, specimens 1 and 2 failed near the junction between the patch and the parent, at the top part of the repair. Specimen 3 failed near the junction between the patch and the parent, at the bottom part of the repair, as shown in Figure 13.

Figure 12: Picture of 3° scarf angle PW repair specimens at RTD (through-the-thickness view)

Figure 13: Picture of 3° scarf angle PW repair specimens at ETD (through-the-thickness view)

5.2 TEST RESULTS OF A 7.5° SCARF ANGLE FOR QUASI-ISOTROPIC SCARF-STEP (C2) REPAIR AT RTD AND ETD

Three specimens were tested at RTD and ETD. Each specimen failed in the adhesive at an average failure stress equal to 270 MPa at RTD and equal to 225 MPa at ETD. This corresponds to a 17% reduction in strength. The stiffness was found to be equal to 43.9 GPa on average at RTD and equal to 43.2 GPa on average. This corresponds to a 1.6% reduction in stiffness. As shown in Figure 14, failure occurred inside the adhesive at RTD and adhesive can be found equally distributed on both parent and patch bonding surfaces. The failure mode is therefore mainly cohesive. The same failure mode was found at ETD.

Figure 14: Picture of 7.5° scarf angle repair specimens at RTD (in-plane view)

5.3 SUMMARY OF THE EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND COMPARISON WITH NUMERICAL RESULTS

Table 7 compares both experimental and numerical results for 3° and 7.5° scarf angle quasi-isotropic scarf-step (C2) repair specimens tested under uniaxial tension at RTD and ETD. First, an insignificant drop of the stiffness was found experimentally when comparing data for both angles between RTD and ETD. At RTD, a restitution of roughly 97% of the stiffness was found for both tested angles when compared to the pristine laminate. Also at RTD, a restitution of 85% of the strength was found for a 3° angle and 34% for a 7.5° angle when compared to the pristine laminate. A drop of 2.3% in strength was found experimentally when comparing data between RTD and ETD for a 3° angle. A more significant drop of 17% was found experimentally when comparing data between RTD and ETD for a 7.5° angle.

Numerically, the stiffness of the repairs was well predicted for both angles. At RTD, for a 3° scarf angle, the predicted failure was underestimated by 12%. The failure type, which was found to occur in the composite material experimentally, was well predicted. This variation might be due to the fact that failure was assumed to occur as soon as the maximum strain criterion was reached in a 0° ply. Also, the scarf angle used for the numerical analysis was idealized. The higher properties found experimentally might be explained by the fact that the real scarf angle was actually lower. At RTD, for a 7.5° scarf angle, the predicted failure was overestimated by 14%. The failure type, which was found to occur in the adhesive experimentally, was well predicted. This variation might be due to the adhesive data that was used for the analyses in ABAQUS. Also, it was assumed that the bondline was perfect without any flaws or voids, and this could have induced a detrimental effect on the strength of the repair measured experimentally. Finally, the scarf angle was idealized as well, and the higher properties found experimentally might be explained by the fact that the real scarf angle was actually higher.

Angle [°]	3		7.5		Pristine (without repair)
Environmental Condition	RTD	ETD	RTD	ETD	RTD
Experimental Stiffness [GPa]	44.4	42.2	43.9	43.2	45.5
Experimental Fail Stress [MPa]	558	545	270	225	653
Numerical Stiffness [GPa]	43.1	-	43.3	-	46.8
Numerical Fail Stress [MPa]	493	-	309	-	-

Table 7: Summary of experimental and numerical results for 3° and 7.5° scarf angle quasi-isotropic scarf-step (C2) repair specimens tested under uniaxial tension at RTD and ETD

6 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented a numerical and experimental study of the behaviour of a plain weave carbon epoxy repaired laminate. Three type of joint were studied, namely scarf-scarf (C1), scarf-step (C2) and step-step (C3), for a 3° scarf angle quasi-isotropic repair.

The elastic analysis revealed that a laminate repaired using configuration C1 is expected to have a higher tensile strength than laminates repaired using configurations C2 or C3. The joint configuration has a strong influence on the failure prediction. It is therefore important to take this parameter into consideration when modeling a scarf joint repair using the finite-element method.

The non-linear elastic-plastic analyses run using ABAQUS/Explicit confirmed the conclusions drawn from the linear elastic analysis. For both 3° and 7.5° scarf angles, configuration C1 had a higher strength value than configuration C2 which had a higher strength value than configuration C3. This analysis also predicted the type of failure of the repaired laminate for each one of the three joint configurations (C1, C2 and C3) as well as for each one of the two scarf angles (3° and 7.5°) using the von Mises yield and shear failure criteria for the adhesive and the maximum strain criterion for the composite. Composite failure is expected to occur for the three joint configurations at a 3° scarf angle. Adhesive failure is expected to occur for the three joint configurations at a 7.5° angle. Three scarf-step (C2) quasi-isotropic repaired specimens were tested in tension at RTD and ETD for both 3° and 7.5° scarf angle. For the 3° scarf angle repair, all specimens failed in the composite material, while for the 7.5° scarf angle repair, all specimens failed in the adhesive. At RTD, a restitution of 85% of the strength was found for a 3° angle scarf and 34% for a 7.5° angle scarf when compared to the pristine laminate. An insignificant drop in stiffness was observed for both angles when compared to the pristine laminate. Temperature was found to have no effect on the observed type of failure. However, temperature was found to have a noticeable effect of the strength of the 7.5° scarf angle repair. The numerical analysis predicted correctly the failure mode of the repaired laminate for both angles at RTD. However, the strength was underestimated by 12% in the case of composite failure (3° scarf angle repair), and over-estimated by 14% in the case of adhesive failure (7.5° scarf angle repair). Parameters such as the scarf angle, bondline quality, and the adhesive and composite material properties might explain these variations. Further studies using microscopy observation of the adhesive bondline of repaired specimens are required in order to model the repair more accurately. Numerical analyses will be conducted to predict the repaired laminate at ETD as well.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. A. Baker, S. Dutton, and D. Kelly, *Composite materials for aircraft structures*, 2nd ed. Reston, VA: American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics, 2004.
- [2] A. J. Gunnion and I. Herszberg, *Parametric study of scarf joints in composite structures*, *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 75, no. 1–4, pp. 364–376, 2006.
- [3] S. B. Kumar, I. Sridhar, S. Sivashanker, S. O. Osiyemi, and A. Bag, *Tensile failure of adhesively bonded CFRP composite scarf joints*, *Mater. Sci. Eng. B*, vol. 132, no. 1–2, pp. 113–120, Jul. 2006.
- [4] A. Marrón, *Scarf joint modeling and analysis of composite materials*, Thesis, Naval Post-Graduate School, Monterey California, 2009.
- [5] R. D. S. G. Campilho, M. F. S. F. de Moura, A. M. G. Pinto, J. J. L. Morais, and J. J. M. S. Domingues, *Modelling the tensile fracture behaviour of CFRP scarf repairs*, *Compos. Part B Eng.*, vol. 40, no. 2, pp. 149–157, Mar. 2009.
- [6] C. Shih-pin, *Finite Element Application for Strength Analysis of Scarf-Patch-Repaired Composite Laminates*, Thesis, Chung Yuan Christian University Taiwan, Dec. 2006.

- [7] I. M. Daniel and O. Ishai, *Engineering mechanics of composite materials*, 2nd ed. New York: Oxford University Press, 2006.
- [8] S. Phillips, *Design of composite bolted and bonded hybrid joints*, CRIAQ Forum Poster, Montreal, Apr. 2014.
- [9] M. C. L. Lee, *Assessment of Adhesive Bonded Repairs*, Thesis, RMIT University, Melbourne Australia, Mar. 2013.
- [10] J. H. L. Pang, *Lead Free Solder: Mechanics and Reliability*, Micro- and Opto-Electronic Materials and Structures: Physics, Mechanics, Design, Reliability, Packaging SE - 12, E. Suhir, Y. C. Lee, and C. P. Wong, Eds. Springer US, pp. 65–88, 2012, 2007.
- [11] E. Ghazali, M.-L. Dano, *Sandwich panel repair and material testing*, CRIAQ Technical Presentation, Montreal, Sept. 2014.